

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11841596>

**SUBJECT: STUDYING METHODS OF STRESS MANAGEMENT IN
INCREASING THE ADAPTABILITY OF STUDENTS TO HIGHER
EDUCATION**

Radjabova Ismigul Rustamovna

senior lecturer of the department of computer systems of the non-governmental educational institution university of economics and pedagogy, independent scientific researcher.

***Annotation.** This article examines the new challenges, problems and opportunities that students who have completed school and secondary specialized education face when adapting to higher education. Modern information technologies are becoming increasingly important in education. In this regard, it is necessary for students to have the opportunity to choose their path and overcome problems when making independent decisions.*

***Key words:** Key words: higher education, flexibility, stress, stress management learning.*

Enter. We know that the student period includes different young people. We can observe many psychological characteristics during this period. It is the students who study far from their parents, in financial stress and under a heavy mental load, who may have negative problems in relations with their peers. A student's longing for home, being scolded by their teachers, unique difficulties in higher education, and even the distance from their peers can cause a student to become stressed.

Coping with stress: Stress levels can be high in higher education. Learning stress management techniques, including meditation, exercise, and recreational activities, can be beneficial for students. Dealing with stress is important for every student in higher education because it helps maintain their mental and physical health. Effective stress management techniques allow students to maintain a balance between their studies and their personal lives. Here are some effective ways to deal with stress:

Physical Activity: Regular exercise is one of the best ways to reduce stress. Exercise stimulates the production of endorphins, which are natural mood enhancers. Activities such as walking, jogging, swimming or yoga can help reduce depression.

Meditation and breathing exercises: Mental exercises such as meditation and deep breathing can help reduce stress levels. These techniques can help you focus and be in the present moment, as well as reduce feelings of anxiety.

Proper nutrition: Proper nutrition increases the body's ability to resist stress. A nutrient-dense, balanced diet can improve brain function and improve overall mood.

Get enough sleep: A healthy sleep pattern plays a very important role in managing stress. Sufficient and quality sleep reduces stress and improves concentration, as well as ensures a proper approach to daily activities.

Occasional Rest: Between studies and other commitments, regular rest is essential for students. This can be done on weekends, doing hobbies, or spending time with friends and family.

Social support network: Getting support from family, friends, and colleagues can help you cope with stress. Social connections improve mental health and play an important role in combating stress.

Self-awareness and reflection: Taking time to understand your feelings and the causes of stress. Keeping a daily or weekly journal to record your feelings and stressful situations can help you manage these situations.

Professional help: If your stress is unmanageable and self-help methods don't work, it's a good idea to consult a psychologist or therapist. These professionals help in reducing stress and developing countermeasures.

Expanding Social Networks: Meeting new people and actively participating in various social networks play an important role in improving students' flexibility. These networks can be useful not only for social, but also for academic and professional interests.

Expanding social networks is an important task for any student during higher education. Extensive social networks open up a variety of opportunities for students, including new friendships, academic collaborations, and future professional connections. Here are some ways to expand your social networks:

Participation in events: Universities and colleges organize many events, seminars and conferences. By participating in these activities, students can meet and expand their connections with people from different fields.

Join clubs and organizations: Various clubs and organizations on campus provide opportunities for students to find and collaborate with friends who share their interests. These organizations help students develop their social and professional skills.

Use of social media platforms: Professional and academic networks can be expanded through social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter. Through these platforms, students can connect with experts in their fields and exchange useful information.

Active participation in group work and projects: Participating in group work with peers allows students to learn each other's skills and collaborate. This helps to build mutual trust and strong relationships.

Attend networking events: Many universities and professional organizations organize special networking events. These events are designed to bring students and professionals closer to each other, get professional advice and expand future opportunities.

Finding Mentors: Finding mentors during your studies can help students gain experience and knowledge in their fields. Mentors are of great importance in providing guidance and direction to students, as well as assisting in professional development.

Taking advantage of international connections and exchange programs: By participating in international exchange programs and international conferences, students can make new connections and learn about different cultures around the world.

The ideas presented above are the works of scientists who have conducted many scientific works and researches in this regard.

REFERENCES.

1. Radjabova I.R. (2024). Components and characteristics of competence of students' adaptability to higher education. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(12), 165–170.

2. Кобыстов Ю.Н. Эмоции, стресс, курение, потребление алкоголя и рак –корреляционные и причинные связи. //Журнал ВНД им. И.П.Павлова. –2007. No 4.

Internet resources.

1) <https://www.studentselect.ai/articles/why-is-adaptability-important-in-higher-education>

2) <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1041608021000832>

3) <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/adaptability-different-resilience-and-heres-how-nurture-it>